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An Investigation of the Handball Attitudes of Secondary School Students in Terms of Some Variables

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the behaviours of secondary school students towards the branch of handball according to some variables. The group of study occurs of a total of 727 students, 424 male and 303 female, who were voluntarily participated in the research and educated in the 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th grades of secondary schools in Gaziosmanpaşa district of Istanbul province in the 2020-2021 academic year. "Handball Attitude Scale for Secondary School Students" developed by Görgüt and Güllü (2017) was used as a datum collection appliance in the study. Statistical analysis of the data has been done with SPSS 26 program, t-test and One Way Anova tests. According to the classes that the students have studied and the sports branches they are interested in; If it is one-way, the One Way Anova test has been used to define the resource of the difference in cases where the relationship between the variables has been significant, and in cases where the variances have been homogeneous, the LSD test, one of the PostHoc tests, has been used. In the research findings, in the LSD tests, it has been revealed that there has been no positive or negative significant difference in the handball branch according to the classes that the students studied, and it has used a positive impact on the handball branch according to the sports branches of interest. ($p < 0.05$). With reference to the conclusions of the t-test performed by looking at the gender of the students, It was concluded that there had been a significant difference between their attitudes towards the branch of handball ($p < 0.05$). However, there has been no significant difference in the attitudes of the students against the branch of handball according to the sports status of the students and the sports status of their parents. It has emerged that the interest of secondary school students and their families in sports does not affect the handball branch positively or negatively.

Keywords: Student, Handball, Physical Education, Attitude, Team Sports

1. Introduction

Activities that attract attention from the masses and require physical activity and sports are also seen as the image of healthy life. In general culture, sports are considered as healthy life, leisure time activities, learning by having fun. The organization, which is held not only for the athlete performing the sportive activity, but also for the audience watching the activity, is the representative of a political, economic and social field (Solmaz & Oguz

Aydın, 2012). In addition to being a tool for individuals to stay healthy and fit, sports is becoming a broad economic sector with each passing day (Yetim, 2014). At the same time, since it is a collective activity, it causes the development of social relations of people and an increase in social participation. By playing a role in bringing people together, sports contribute to the development of freedom consciousness and increase the solidarity and cooperation among people (Kat, 2009). Sports can be defined as improving the mental and physical health of people, which is the basic element in social, economic and cultural development, supporting the development of character and personality traits, ensuring adaptation to the environment by gaining talent, knowledge and skills, providing cohesion, solidarity and peace between individuals and societies in the international arena, fighting, competing and getting excited within the framework of certain rules by increasing the fighting power of individuals and activities to gain superiority in competition. In this context, today's sport is a very useful, versatile, universalized phenomenon with various purposes and dimensions (Soyer et al., 2010).

Sport, which improves the physical and mental health of the person, is also a pedagogical, biological and social factor that regulates the social behavior of the person and increases the motoric and mental characteristics at a certain level. In other words, sports is one of the most important social factors that ensure the development of the soul, body and idea of the person, the coordination between them and socialization. Also, since sports appeal to the human element, whether it is aimed at creating a healthy society, whether it is a tool that can be used for social dissolution and alienation, whether it is aimed to raise innovative, constructive youth who can look to the future with confidence, today, it is undeniable that sports are an indispensable and effective social phenomenon (Yetim, 2014).

Sportive behaviors in individuals contribute to their development in every way. Participating in sports games as a team player enables the development of feelings such as working together with time, mutual assistance, game order and respect for other players. Working as a team teaches the individual how to act in this environment. It is accepted that team sports strengthen the bonds and social relations between people and groups and shorten social distances (Taşkıran, 1997). Handball, as in many sports, is an activity created by various movements, aiming to gain superiority over the opponent and to play well together with each team's teammates at the possible level (Bağırhan, 1990). Handball, successfully develops the athlete's movement habits and his/her collective thinking skills. During the game, the athletes have to harmonize their wishes with the requirements of the team and are directed to cooperate. As a result of this, they learn that they can achieve success only through collective play and cooperation. As it is aimed in sportive games, it is also aimed to develop the ability of individuals to act independently in the branch of handball. The handball branch is also very effective in personality training. In particular, it provides the development of the qualities of courage, honesty, willpower and perseverance (Sevim, 2002).

People are in constant communication and interaction with both themselves and their environment from the moment of birth. As a result of this, they can develop attitudes towards events, objects, groups or streams of ideas. Attitude is a mood, state or attitude that directs the behavior of individuals towards a thought or event. In other words, attitude is a mental, physical, behavioral and emotional reaction that an individual organizes based on his/her motivation, ability, experience and knowledge against an event, object or social issue in his/her environment (İnceoğlu, 2011).

The common point in the definitions made about attitude is that attitude is a preliminary predisposition that is understood by the individual's reactions to the social events around his/her. Attitude, first of all, expresses the social attitude. In addition, the concept of attitude also expresses the readiness for a reaction behavior and the continuous systematic organization of knowledge and emotions for the realization of the attitude consisting of cognitive, behavioral and emotional elements.

The individual is able to form an attitude towards the objects located around him/her. These objects can be a business, a profession, a political opinion, a public organization, a region and a course. For example, an individual may develop an attitude towards the site management, supermarkets, doctors, political parties, grocery stores, and similar objects in the region where he/she lives. If the attitude developed towards the object is in a positive direction, positive behaviors such as appreciating, loving, supporting the object are exhibited.

Otherwise, in adverse situations, negative behaviors such as moving away from the object and avoidance are exhibited (İnceoğlu, 2011).

By explaining the basic concepts of the study, it is aimed to investigate the attitudes of secondary school students representing different segments of the society identified as the target group in the study towards the branch of handball in terms of some variables.

2. Method

The purpose of this study is to examine the attitudes of secondary school students against the branch of handball according to some variables. The group of the research consists of a total of 727 students, 424 male and 303 female, who were voluntarily participated in the study and who are studying in the 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th grades of secondary schools in Gaziosmanpaşa borough of Istanbul city in the 2020-2021 academic year.

2.1 Data Collection Tool

In the research, the “Handball Attitude Scale for Secondary School Students” developed by Görgüt and Güllü (2017) has been used to define the injury anxiety levels of the athletes as a data collection tool (Görgüt & Mehmet, 2017) The scale used consists of 16 items. There is not negative (conflicting) item on the scale. It is scored as I strongly disagree 1, I disagree 2, I am indecisive 3, I agree 4, and I strongly agree 5, on a 5-point Likert-type scale. High marks obtained from the scale specify that students have a positive attitude towards handball.

2.2 Analysis of Data

By transferring the obtained data to IBM SPSS 26 program, reliability, frequency, percentile slices, arithmetic averages and standard deviations have been computational. In order to determine the assumption of normal distribution of the data, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test has been used for the analysis of independent variables (Büyüköztürk et al., 2011; Büyüköztürk, 2011). As a result of the results obtained, kurtosis and skewness values have been also examined (Büyüköztürk et al., 2011; Büyüköztürk, 2011; George & Mallery, 2010). As a result of the analysis, these values have been found to be between -1.5 and +1.5. For this reason, it has been determined that it provides the assumption of normality (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). Parametric tests have been used for the analysis and interpretation of the data. In this direction, t-test analysis was carried out to explain the attitudes of the students towards the handball branch according to gender. According to the classes that the students have studied and the sports fields that the students are interested in, one-way Anova test has been used if it is one-way. When a significant difference has been found in the relationship between the variables used, the LSD test, one of the PostHoc tests, has been used to determine the source of this difference, provided that the variances have been homogeneous.

3. Findings

In this part of the research, the statistical analysis results of the data obtained from the Handball Branch Attitude scale applied to the participants have been interpreted in terms of some variables by tabulating them.

3.1 Descriptive Qualities

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distributions of the Research Group's Descriptive Qualities Regarding Handball Branch Attitudes.

Variables	<i>f</i>	%	
Gender	Male	424	58.3
	Woman	303	41.7
Class	5th grade	173	23.8
	6th grade	284	39.1

	7th grade	148	20.4
	8th grade	122	16.8
Status of Doing Sports in Family Members	Yes	305	42.0
	No	422	58.0
Active Sports Status of Students	I do active sports	297	40.9
	I don't do sports	430	59.1
Sports Branches That Students Are Interested In	football	242	33.3
	basketball	89	12.2
	volleyball	121	16.6
	Handball	9	1,2
	Gymnastics	12	1.7
	Karate	20	2.8
	taekwondo	49	6.7
	wrestling	6	8
	Swimming	123	16.9
	Other	56	7.7

When Table-1, which contains the data on the descriptive demographic qualities of secondary school students, is examined, 424 of the students participating in the research are male and 303 are female. Looking at the class variables, it is seen that 173 of the students participating in the research are in the 5th grade, 284 are in the 6th grade, 148 are in the 7th grade, and 122 are in the 8th grade. It is seen that 297 of the participants do active sports, 430 people do not do active regular sports, and 42% of their family members do active sports, 58% are those who do not do sports. When looking at the sports branches that students are interested in, it is seen that 242 people are interested in football, 89 people are interested in basketball, 121 people are interested in volleyball, 9 people are interested in handball, 12 people are interested in gymnastics, 20 people are interested in karate, 49 people are interested in taekwondo, 6 people are interested in wrestling, 123 people are interested in swimming and 56 people are those who are interested in other sports branches.

The results of the t-test analysis conducted to determine the statistical differences between the Handball Branch attitudes of the participants studying in secondary school and their gender are given in Table-2.

Table 2: T-Test results of secondary school students according to their gender and attitude scores related to handball branch.

Variables	Groups	N	x	ss	t test		
					t	sd	p
Gender	Male	424	3.44	1.10	6.81	597	.001*
	Woman	303	2.83	1.25			

* Significant difference at $p < 0.05$ level

When the handball branch attitudes of the participants given in Table-2 are analyzed by gender, it is seen that there is a significant difference between men and women ($t[597]=6,81$; $p < 0,05$). It is seen that male students' handball attitudes ($X=3.44$) are higher than female students' attitudes ($X=2.83$).

The t-test analysis results conducted to determine the statistical differences between the handball branch attitude scores of the secondary school students according to their doing sports status are given in Table-3.

Table 3: T-Test results of the handball branch attitude scores of the secondary school students according to their doing sports status.

Variables	Groups	N	x	ss	t test		
					t	sd	p
Doing Sports Situations	I do active sports	338	3.12	1.23	-1,427	713	.153*
	I don't do sports	377	3.25	1.17			

* Significant difference at $p < 0.05$ level

When the handball branch attitude scores of the participants given in Table-3 are examined according to their doing sports status, there is no statistically significant difference according to the difference in the students' doing sports status ($t[713] = -1,427$; $p > 0,05$). Those who do active sports are seen as 3.12 ± 1.23 , while those who do not do sports are seen as 3.25 ± 1.17 .

The results of the t-test analysis conducted to determine the statistical differences between the handball branch attitude scores according to doing sports status of the family members of the secondary school students are given in Table-4.

Table 4: T-Test results of the handball branch attitude scores according to doing sports status of the family members of the secondary school students.

Variables	Groups	N	x	ss	t test		
					t	sd	p
Doing sports status in family members	Yes	314	3.13	1.22	-1,072	725	.284
	No	413	3.23	1.19			

* Significant difference at $p < 0.05$ level

When the handball branch attitude scores of the participants given in Table 4 are examined according to doing sports status of the family members, there is no statistically significant difference according to the difference in doing sports status of the family members ($t[725] = -1,072$; $p > 0,05$). Family members who do active sports are seen as 3.13 ± 1.22 , while those who do not do active sports are seen as 3.23 ± 1.19 .

The results of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether or not the handball branch attitudes of secondary school students differ according to the classes they study are given in Table-5.

Table 5: Anova results of the handball branch attitude scale scores according to the grades of the students.

School Type	N	x	ss	Source of Variance	KT	sd	KO	F	p	meaningfulness
5th grade (1)	173	3.15	1,174	Between G.	0.4	3	0.133	.091	.965	
6th grade (2)	284	3.19	1,230	Within G.	1059.139	723	1,465			
7th grade (3)	148	3.22	1,191	Total	1059,540	726				
8th grade (4)	122	3.20	1,234							
Total	727	*	.1,208							

When Table-5 is examined, it does not show a statistically significant difference according to the classes of secondary school students ($F = .091$; $p > .05$).

The results of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether or not the handball branch attitudes of secondary school students differ according to the sports branches they are interested in are given in Table-6.

Table 6: Anova results of the handball branch attitude scale scores according to the sports branches that students are interested in.

School Type	N	x	ss	Source of Variance	KT	sd	KO	F	p	meaningfulness
football (1)	242	3.38	1.092	Between G.	27,308	9	3.034			
basketball (2)	89	3.07	1.198	Within G.	1032.232	717	1.440			
volleyball (3)	121	2.99	1,284	Total	1059,540	726				
Handball (4)	9	2.88	1,364							
gymnastics (6)	12	2.45	1,233							1-2,3,6,8;
Karate (7)	20	3.07	1,248					2.108	.027	10-6; 11-6
taekwondo (8)	49	2.94	1,191							
wrestling (9)	6	2.91	1.685							
Swimming (10)	123	3.26	1,194							
Other (11th)	56	3.31	1,363							
Total	727	3.19	1,208							

When Table-6 is examined, it shows a statistically significant difference according to the sports branches that secondary school students are interested in ($F=2.108$; $p<0.05$).

According to the results of the LSD test conducted to determine that the "handball branch attitudes" differ according to the sports branches that the participants are interested in, it has been determined that the students who are interested in football ($X=3,38$) have higher attitudes towards basketball ($X=3.07$), volleyball ($X=2,99$), gymnastics ($X=2,45$), taekwondo ($X=2,94$) and handball branches. It is seen that the attitudes of the students who are interested in swimming sport towards the handball branch are higher than the attitudes of those who are interested in Gymnastics ($X=2,45$) and other branches. There is no significant difference among sports branches such as basketball ($X=3,07$), volleyball ($X=2,99$), handball ($X=2,88$), gymnastics ($X=2,45$), karate ($X=3,07$), taekwondo ($X=2,94$) and wrestling ($X=2,91$) in the context of handball branch attitudes and behaviors.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

In the study, the handball branch attitudes of secondary school students have been examined in terms of gender, class, the status of doing sports in family members, active sports status of students and the sports branches that students are interested in. No studies have been found in the literature on the determination of attitudes towards the branch of handball. It is seen that the studies generally focus on physical education lessons and sportive activities. Since the handball branch is also a sportive activity, the findings of the study are discussed as follows. According to the gender variable and the scores of the attitude dimensions of the students of the secondary schools in Gaziosmanpaşa, Istanbul, who have participated in this study (Table 2), it has been seen that the male students' attitude scores towards the handball branch have been significantly different and their scores have been higher than that of the female students ($p < 0,05$). In similar studies in the literature, studies supporting the findings of our study have been found.

In the studies conducted by Smoll and Schutz, 1980 and Kangalgil et al., 2006, (Kangalgil et al., 2006; Smoll & Schutz, 1980) a difference which supports our study has been found in favor of male students in the mean scores of attitudes towards gender. It has been determined that male students' attitude levels are higher than female students. In the study conducted by (Tomik et al., 2012), it has been determined that male students have shown higher attitudes towards sports and physical education than female students. In the study conducted by Türkmen and his/her friends (2016) and examining the attitudes of university students towards sports, it has been determined that there has been a significant difference between the gender variable of the students and their attitudes towards sports. In the study, it has been observed that male students have had higher attitudes than females. Similarly, in the study conducted by Singh and Devi (2013) (RK & Devi, 2013), it has been determined that the participant students' attitudes towards sports branches and game activities have been positive, and that male participants have shown positive and higher attitudes than women. In the study conducted by Yıldız and his/her friends (2017). (Yıldız et al., 2017), differences in favor of men have been determined according to gender in the total attitude scores of the participants towards sports. These studies support the findings of our study. In the study conducted by (Şişko & Demirhan, 2002), it has been determined that there has been no significant difference between male and female participants in terms of student attitudes ($p > 0,05$). It can be stated that these findings do not support the results of our study.

In the study, when the handball branch attitude scores of secondary school students (Table-3) have been examined according to their doing sports status, It has been determined that there has been no statistically significant difference according to the variable of students' doing sports status ($p > 0,05$). In studies conducted in the literature, it has been determined that there has been a significant difference in favor of those who do sports (Kangalgil et al., 2006; Koçak, 2014; Türkmen et al., 2016; Yıldız et al., 2017). These results do not seem to support the findings of our study. The probable reason for this difference is that the studies have been conducted with university student participants other than secondary school students.

In the study, it has been determined that there has been no statistically significant difference in the handball branch attitude scores of secondary school students (Table-4) according to the variable of doing sports status of family members ($p > 0,05$). The findings of the studies conducted in this field in the literature contradict the findings of our study. In the study conducted by (Kotan et al., 2009), It has been observed that if one of the family members plays sports, students are encouraged to play sports according to the students who do not play sports in their family. In the study conducted by (Serarslan & Akkaya, 2000) it has been determined that there has been a significant difference in the attitude scores of secondary school students according to the variable of family members' doing sports status. As a result of the study conducted by (Sunay & Seda Saracaloğlu, 2003) with 451 athletes from 15 different sports branches, it has been determined that family members have been the first to encourage them to do sports. In the study conducted by (Baxter-Jones & Maffulli, 2003), the effect of families on the participation of athletes in sports has been examined. As a result of the study, it has been seen that the effect of the families of the athletes has been high in starting sports. In the study conducted by [Atalay and his/her friends \(2015\)](#), It has been determined that the fact that there is someone who does sports in the family of the participants causes a significant difference in their attitudes towards sports. The findings of these studies contradict with the findings of our study. The main reason for this can be shown as the increasing interest

of students in sports with each passing time. In the study, It has been determined that the handball branch attitude scores of secondary school students (Table-5) haven't shown a statistically significant difference according to the class variable ($p>0,05$). It is seen that there are studies in the literature that support the results of our study. Accordingly, in the study conducted by (Hergüner et al., 1997), It has been determined that sports do not affect the communication skills of students and there has been no significant difference in comparisons made in terms of variables such as between classes, between departments, parents' educational status, marital status, number of family members, social activities and income status. In the study conducted by (Kızılyallı, 2012), and examining the opinions of female university students about participation in sports activities, It has been determined that there has been no significant difference between the opinions of the students in the preparatory class and the 4th grade in the average of attitude scores according to the class variable. It is seen that the results of these studies support the findings of our study.

In the study, it has been determined that the handball branch attitude scores of secondary school students (Table-6) have shown a statistically significant difference according to the sports branches that the students are interested in ($p<0.05$). Since there is no study in the literature based on the variable of sports branches that students are interested in, we haven't had the opportunity to compare the findings of our study.

As a result, it has been tried to reach a conclusion about the attitudes of the secondary school students towards the handball branch according to the variables of gender, class, doing sports status in family members, active sports status of the students and the sports branches that the students are interested in. It has been determined that the handball branch attitudes of secondary school students have been positively affected by the variables of gender and the sports branches that students are interested in, but the variables of class, doing sports status in family members, active sports status of students haven't had a positive or negative effect on handball branch attitudes. Although it can be said that the attitudes of the participant students towards the handball branch are at a good level, a large-scale investigation of the attitudes towards the handball branch will contribute to the spread of this sport branch to large masses if similar studies are carried out on students with different education levels.

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